

Spatial Invariance, Special Relativity and the Quantum Wave

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 10, 2022

Newtonian mechanics (from the 1600s) defines a quantity called momentum p in terms of mv where m is mass and $v=dx/dt$ with dx and dt tending to zero. Newton's first law is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the absence of a force. The second demonstrates how p changes under a force. If one has equal action/reaction then overall momentum is conserved. As a consequence the idea of a "wave" associated with p does not arise. The main focus is on the idea of force.

Fermat's Least Time Principle for light (1600s), however, is based on minimizing the overall time traveled by light which reflects or refracts. Young's interference experiments did not occur until the very early 1800s and Newton considered light to be a particle at this time. In fact light bounces off a foil creating an impact like a particle. Fermat's principle does not directly make use of momentum or its conservation. It is focused on minimizing time. To do so, however, one must take a derivative with respect to a certain variable and set it equal to 0. This variable is the spatially invariant one in a problem. For example consider reflection (stationary or moving mirror) or refraction in two dimensions x,y . Let the mirror or medium face lie along the x axis at $y=0$. There exists a constraint on y and given a fixed starting point one cannot change y . This leaves x to be varied because it is invariant. Thus the extremization of time is really a statement of invariance of a spatial variable. In other words, Fermat's principle is linked to the physical variables t and x while Newton's focuses on p (momentum).

This invariance in turn gives rise to conservation of momentum in the direction of the invariant variable i.e. (px) . There is still the idea of Newton's change in momentum as (py) abruptly changes in refraction as it hits the interface of media.

The point we wish to make is that from Fermat's least time principle one sees that conservation of momentum in the absence of a force is completely intertwined with invariance in space. The two cannot be separated in this approach and there is nothing unphysical about t or x . In fact, one may create a function $A = -Et + (px)x + (py)y$ such that dA/dx partial = $px =$ conserved quantity. In this function (px) and x are on the same footing. One does not have one without the other. This idea is carried over into special relativity as $-Et + p \cdot r$ is a Lorentz invariant.

Given that p momentum is physical (it manifests itself in impulse hits) and p and x are inseparable in $(px)x$ we suggest there should exist a physical manifestation in x i.e. in space linked to the maintenance of conservation of momentum in this direction even in the absence of a force. This we argue leads to the physical idea of a wavelength which follows from $A = -Et + px$ with $A=0$ in all constant velocity frames leading to a frequency proportional to $1/E$ and wavelength to $1/p$.

We have discussed these ideas in previous notes, but the main point we wish to make here is that equivalence of spatial invariance in the x direction in Fermat's principle with conservation of momentum in the same direction suggests that if p is physical, the spatial invariance must also be manifested physically. It is not simply a mathematical convenience to link t to x to px , we argue.

Furthermore this wavelength should be linked to establishing conservation of momentum as it does in quantum mechanics where the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\int \exp(-ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) dx$ automatically ensures $p_1 = p_2$ without imposing momentum conservation a priori as in Newton's first law.

Both Newtonian mechanics and Fermat's principle suggest that p may change abruptly due to a force or an immediate change in medium. The idea of a physical wavelength, however, suggests there may be interactions completely different from an abrupt change in p due to an impulse. In particular there may be interference or Bohm-Aharonov interactions.

Newtonian Mechanics

The idea of invariance in space associated with a conserved momentum is already present in Newton's first law which states that a particle at rest or with a constant velocity retains this behaviour unless acted on by a force. Momentum is mv nonrelativistically so it is conserved. In this theory, however, conservation of momentum is not intertwined with spatial invariance, rather the focus is entirely on force. The second law shows how momentum changes with a force: $dp/dt = \text{Force}(x)$ and if one has action/reaction i.e. F on a particle leads to $-F$ on the delivering body then overall momentum is again conserved.

As noted $p = mv$ (nonrelativistically) and $v = dx/dt$ where dx and dt both tend to 0 i.e. extremely tiny values. In particular these values are much smaller than \hbar/p which is used to describe a wavelength for both light and a particle in quantum mechanics. In principle one may describe Newtonian mechanics in terms of a variational principle as shown in (1) which makes use of variations of time and in turn x , an invariant spatial variable. We discuss this in a later section.

Fermat's Principle

Fermat's principle for light like Newton's was developed in the 1600s before the wave behaviour of light was known. (Young's experiments occurred at the beginning of the 1800s).. Fermat's principle states that light travels in such a way that it minimizes overall time where $\text{distance} = \text{speed} * \text{time}$. This principle may be applied to reflection from stationary or moving mirrors or refraction to cite a few examples. A main point is that no mention of momentum or its conservation is made. (In Newtonian mechanics minimization of time or invariance of x is not used.)

No mention of invariance is also made in Fermat's statement of extremizing time, yet the principle is based on varying a spatially invariant variable which leads directly to conservation of momentum in this direction. Thus a main point we wish to make is that an invariant spatial variable in the problem is equivalent to conservation of momentum in that direction, the two are intertwined. If (px) is physical, then spatial invariance should be physically established in the x direction and should lead to conservation of momentum in this direction. This is a completely different notion from stating conservation of momentum a priori. It is also a stronger statement than simply writing $(px)_x$ and taking $d/dx \rightarrow d/dx (px)_x = (px)$ and stating that d/dx is linked to spatial invariance if one establishes an equation with 0. The reason we argue that the link between p and x is so strong in this situation is that this relationship also holds in special

relativity for which $A = -Et+px$ is an invariant. (p,E) and (x,t) transform in the same manner and so $p = \gamma m_0 v$ and $E = \gamma m_0 c^2$ should also have a physical representation in $x-t$ i.e. a frequency proportional to $1/E$ and a wavelength to $1/p$ with \hbar as the constant.

The above idea is unusual because p and E are defined in terms of rest mass and $v = dx/dt$. No matter the frame, dx and dt tend to zero yet \hbar/E and \hbar/p are much larger than dx , dt . For example in Newtonian mechanics one has $V(x)$ which holds at each x . $V(x)$ may be used in special relativity and quantum mechanics suggesting there is resolution finer than \hbar/p for a given p .

The idea that E and p may be expressed either in terms $v = dx/dt$ with $dx, dt \rightarrow 0$ or linked with frequency = \hbar/E and wavelength = \hbar/p suggests two different viewpoints which we argue represent particle-wave duality.

Maupertuis' Principle

One may argue that the ideas of Fermat's principle apply to light which is not a particle with rest mass. Very similar arguments, however, appear in Maupertuis' principle (1) which seeks an extrema of:

$$\Delta \int_{(t_a, t_b)} dt \sum (i) p(i) dq(i)/dt \quad ((A))$$

$p(i) dq(i)/dt = m(v_x v_x + v_y v_y)$ for a two dimensional problem and Delta applies to finding a stationary path. Imagine a constant potential V_1 for $y > 0$ and a constant potential V_2 for $y \leq 0$. "Y" has a constraint so x is again an invariant variable. For a fixed starting and end point one varies x in the exact manner as in Fermat's principle and again finds conservation of momentum in the x direction. In particular one has $m v_i \cdot v_i$ in each regions multiplied by t_i for each region and extremizes:

$$M v_1 v_1 t_1 + M v_2 v_2 t_2 \text{ or } m v_1 \frac{d}{dx} (x x + y a y a) + m v_2 \frac{d}{dx} ((x_b - x)(x_b - x) + y b y b) = 0$$

Here $(0, y_a)$ and (x_b, y_b) are the starting and endpoints.

Thus the ideas of Fermat's principle and of Maupertuis' coincide and deal with the variables x and t (which are physical) and lead to a conclusion regarding px . In other words the idea of x and p being intertwined which may be extended to $-Et+px$ in special relativity holds for both light and particles with rest mass.

One might argue that the physical reality is the conservation law i.e. px constant, but the variables t and x are just as physical as momentum. Thus we argue that there is no reason not to expect that invariance in x be manifested by p and x being linked i.e. through a wavelength = \hbar/p .

A Wave Maintaining Conservation of Momentum In the Absence of Force

As we have previously noted, if spatial invariance leads to momentum conservation in Fermat's principle and p and x are considered on the same footing and both are physical, then the physical nature of " x " i.e. the wavelength should lead to conservation of momentum in free space for a free particle without having to impose this conservation idea as done in Newton's first law.

We have noted before that the form $A = -Et + px$ which defines, up to a constant factor, frequency and wavelength, is Lorentz invariant and represents both the relativistic and nonrelativistic free particle action with $v = x/t$. We have also noted that an eigenvalue equation:

$$-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

leads to conservation of momentum:

$$\int dx \exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(ipx) = 0 \text{ unless } p_1 = p \text{ i.e. conservation} \quad ((2))$$

In ((2)) one does not have to impose a priori momentum conservation in terms of the absence of an impulse type force which changes the p vector.

The Intertwining of (p,E) and (x,t) and New Interactions

The intertwining of p,E and x,t leading to the idea of physical frequency and wavelength also leads to the notion of interactions beyond impulse type forces existing both in Newtonian mechanics and Fermat's/Maupertuis' principles. If a wavelength is physically manifested and occurs over a length of \hbar/p then the particle is probabilistically found within this region, but has $p = mv$ (nonrelativistically). Thus an impulse hit may still occur, but the probabilistic form over \hbar/p may be disturbed by objects of the same size i.e. a single or multi-slit system of the scale of a wavelength. This leads to unusual interference type patterns. Furthermore two particles with the same momentum may be phase-shifted which also leads to an interference pattern.

Conclusion

In conclusion we suggest that Newton's theory contains both momentum and its conservation. Momentum only changes when a particle is acted on by a force. Thus the main focus is on a force.

In Fermat's principle the main focus is on extremizing time for reflecting/refracting light, but this is equivalent to varying an spatially invariant variable x if the mirror/medium lies in the x direction. Thus Fermat's least time principle could be called Fermat's Spatially Invariant principle. This in turn leads to conservation of momentum in the direction of the invariant variable. Thus three variables: time, x and (px) are strongly linked.

The link with Newtonian mechanics is that there is no force in the direction of the spatially invariant variable (i.e. no medium change) so momentum should be conserved.

At first one might argue that given Newton's conservation of momentum in the x direction one may create Fermat's principle mathematically which is true. Alternatively given Fermat's principle one may create Newton's concept of conserved momentum in the direction of the spatially invariant variable. Thus it seems that there may be a physical manifestation beyond simply taking a constant (px) multiplying it by x and then taking d/dx and claiming spatial invariance if the derivative over more than one path leads to 0.

A reason this may be more than simply a math operation is that the form $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant. Thus p and x are intertwined also through special relativity. Thus we suggest that if p,E are physical, the intertwining with x,t should also be physical. In other words $E=mvcc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=mov/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ with $v=dx/dt$ and $dx,dt \rightarrow 0$. On the other hand there is a direct link with space and time due to invariance $-Et+px$ so there is a frequency $=\hbar/E$ and wavelength $=\hbar/p$. These values do not tend to 0 thus there is a duality i.e the particle wave duality.

As a result a free particle has a momentum p, but is probabilistically distributed within repeatable wavelength units described through the eigenvalue equation: $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. This suggests new interactions which may occur beyond Newton's rapid impulse hit or Fermat's p change due to a rapid medium change. In other words there may be wavelength related interactions such as interference. Furthermore the eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle automatically ensures momentum conservation. It does not need to be introduced a priori because no force is present in the x direction.

References

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